

Action Research on The Effectiveness of Education in Emergency (EIE) online teaching and learning: Perception of parents at primary school level

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ABSTRACT: Online learning has been implemented in the primary schools in the times of lockdown due to Covid 19. It had dramatically changed the learning process and the manner of delivery of lesson by the teachers. This style of learning was experienced by the students in government primary schools in Bhutan for the first time under compulsion. With the lack of technologies and knowledge by both parents and students, it was challenging to cope with learning. For this reason the aim of this study was to investigate the parent's perception of online learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and acceptability. There are 185 parents of Wangdue Pry School student who were randomly selected for this study. Quantitative questionnaires were used to collect data and analyzed. The study has shown that EIE online learning was effective if parents and learners both collaborate and if the resources are abundant. There was positive illustration to different variables of diverse background, flexibility, accessibility and time and resources to EIE online learning. The study concluded that primary schools can also implement EIE online learning with proper direction and clear instruction from the teachers if there is another lockdown due to pandemic.

INTRODUCTION

The schools around the world are closed due to Covid 19 pandemic and the schooling for millions of students has been interrupted. The Covid 19 virus is devastating every corner of the world indiscriminately with huge losses of life and economic disruption. It has affected everyone equally. We have seen our students staying at home for months. They are restless they can't go to school or they are not allowed to play outside. Education that took place over the Internet which is often referred to as "e-learning" is defined as online learning. With the lockdown and closure of the school, 20 Dzongkhags students were left at home. The prolonged closure of schools is going to impact every child of different key stages. Therefore to facilitate students to continue learning EiE was developed with a prioritized curriculum. This study intends to see the challenges faced by the parents of primary students in coping up with online learning at home. What are the perceptions of the parents on the new approaches? Are parents satisfied with EiE learning or they prefer the old methods of learning face to face in the classroom? With the pandemic of 2020, it will force new laws, regulations, and solutions for future countries, governments, and populations to be more prepared than today (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020). So the transition to online teaching and learning will benefit everyone in the future. As stated by Lu (2017) knowledge cannot be attended spontaneously but through deeper learning through knowledge sharing and by cultivation.

Research Questions

- i. What is the perception of parents on level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and acceptability?
- ii. How can the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning enhanced?

Research Objectives

- i. To study parents' perception on level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and acceptability.
- ii. To provide a set of measures and guidelines to different stakeholders for the Enhancement of the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

EIE teaching and learning during Covid 19

E-learning has become a gradually important teaching and learning approaches but it has also recently extended to primary and secondary schools due to the pandemic. E-learning has been implemented successfully in developed countries but countries like Bhutan most of the teachers, parents, and students are not fully technologically conversant. Computers and smartphones are the

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most essential tools to implement eLearning successful but some people, especially those living in rural areas are computer and technologically illiterate hindering the implementation of eLearning in Bhutan. As of now, online Learning apps and Tools: Wechat, Messenger, Gmail, Google classroom, Google sheets were used for the students to practice and then assess their knowledge of content and concepts taught. Online teaching is the most challenging methods of teaching where the teachers as well as students have to overcome barriers such as technology, time, environment, resources and learning diversity. The teachers have a huge responsibility in providing instructional learning resources and activities available to the students and create an effective, efficient, and appealing learning environment instead of just providing the instructions. The study by Bailey & b, (2009) states that the experienced instructors execute social roles like welcoming and encouraging students to share their experiences, understanding and recognizing the challenges faced by the students in coping up with online teaching. Nevertheless, a study conducted by Kogeda & Anele, (2013) on “Factors affecting E-learning in Southern Africa” states that the attitude, lack of skills to apply e-learning and being unfriendly to the use of ICT for learning by the teachers are often seen as a barrier to the implementation of eLearning. From the previous works of literature, we identified three variables seen by different researchers to see the perception of the parents on the learning outcome and learning experiences with EiE. These variables are diverse background, flexibility, and acceptability as they are the factors that affect learners learning. These variables can play a significant role in EiE context.

Diverse Background

Learning has been made very easy for students but how far. Our learners came from uneducated families, different catchment areas and different cultural background. We also have special children who need more attention. Lower primary student needs parent’s guidance for online learning and most of the parents are uneducated. Those educated parents don’t have time to guide their children. With the rise in infectious diseases, most of the countries had to shut down the schools. In a situation where the students are not allowed to go to school, they opted for online education. Learning through online became convenient but it also brought challenges like; accessibility of internet, availability of computers or smartphones and guidance in learning. Parents being technologically illiterate had difficulty in operating and guiding their children to learn. Textbook learning resources are suitable for enhancing lower order to mid-order cognitive processes like remembering, understanding, applying and analyzing but it does not facilitate high order skills in Bloom’s Taxonomy. As stated by Hameed, Shaikh, Hameed, and Shamim (2016) those students who are not exposed to computer faces many problems during eLearning. So computer interaction should be considered while designing learning for students. With the change in learning patterns children should also opt to learn online and depend less on textbooks. For those children who needed more support from teacher to understand, and children whose mother tongue is different, they needed the most support of a teacher.

Flexibility

E-learning has changed the teaching method from teacher-centered to student centered approach, where students can access the materials anytime and anywhere due to the technological platforms. Unlike traditional classroom students can control their learning pace and path. The result from the case study conducted by (Sagheb-Tehrani), 2009 also showed that the best advantage of online courses was “Flexibility” from the student’s perspective. Flexibility in terms of time also reduces the workload of parents and the cost of travelling. The flexibility of time allows the students to access the content anytime as per their own convenience and at their own pace which enables active participation, continual knowledge building while learning at their best learning readiness time. Moreover, the result from the study by Shonfeld & Ronen (2015), confirmed that Flexibility in the online teaching and learning allows time management and access to information as per their attention spans and concentration limitations. The findings also showed that the online course empowered all students to take responsibility, to devote the time and develop self-discipline that led to learning. However, due to lack of connectivity, downloading, writing and submitting the activities becomes slow leading to frustrations among the learners which affects the ease of learning. As different students adopts different level and type of learning strategies, getting the right design of tasks, assessment and feedback were regarded as the most imperative. In a study conducted by (Lim, nd) on “The Effect of Flexible Learning Schedule on Online Learners’ Learning, Application, and Instructional Perception”, the most frequently received comment on the likeness of flexible learning schedule were the control of time and learning processes. The flexible timing to take the online courses, less stressful and rushed but the procrastination was one of the negative effect of flexibility in taking online lessons. Same as this, many of the students also procrastinate in submission of their assignments which leads to increase in the number of their assignments and more stress on them.

Acceptability and learning

Teachers are seen as the font of knowledge as long as students acknowledge what they learned and ready to receive knowledge. A study by Abdallah (2018) showed the result of parent’s perception on eLearning that it had improved the quality of students learning by providing to them with variety of accessibility of learning materials.

E-learning process is affected by many factors such as the subject, knowledge level of the learners, and the environment. There are some of the factors that can hinder eLearning such as awareness of the parents on online learning. Then computer literacy and the digital divide (Owuor and Anele, 2013) can also be another obstacle to both parents and students to accept eLearning. This causes

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setbacks in the implementation of EiE learning which also causes anxiety in some children. Children have to decide which information is important for them but Abdallah (2018) also stated that eLearning doesn't limit students or confine in any manner, regarding course materials, availability of faculty members, accessibility, and time-related issues. It depends only on the receiver because the major factor that affects the eLearning process is the amount of information the users are prepared to receive. Students' interaction also played greater impact on student learning outcomes as per result found by Anh (2017). Verma et al (2020) also states that elearning is a cheap and feasible method that helps gain knowledge, maintaining routine and improving the morale of both teachers and student

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Instrument

A quantitative descriptive survey method was adopted to study the parents' perception on effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in primary school. For this, questionnaire was administered to collect the data. Few open-ended questions were also provided to find some measures and guidelines to enhance the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning and content analysis was carried out. Likert scale was used to collect and measure the variables in this study.

Participants

The study was conducted with the parents of the students studying in classes' PP to 6 in Wangdue Primary School. The sample of 185 parents was randomly selected based on the accessibility on Wechat.

Data collection tools and procedures

Questionnaire with some open-ended questions was used to collect data and to enable quantitative analysis of data obtained from the field. The Likert scale consisting of 5 levels such as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree were used. The students will use (✓) against the level they feel they fall under.

The data was tabulated and data entered was then analyzed using descriptive statistics. The general information was analyzed using descriptive statistics involving frequencies and percentages. The level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Content analysis was conducted to seek some actionable measures and guidelines to enhance the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning.

RESULT

The result analysis of the research was exhibited in the following manner.

4.1 General Information

4.2 The level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability.

4.3 Analysis on measures and guidelines for the enhancement of the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning.

4.1 General Information

The demographic information of the parents such as gender, level of education and family income was represented in table

4.1. The data was interpreted using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentage.

Table 4. 1 Frequency and Percentage of parent's general information

General Information		Frequency	Percentage
1. Gender	Male	72	38.9
	Female	113	61.1
	Total	185	100.0
2. Education Level	PhD	13	7.0
	Master's degree	6	3.2
	Bachelor's degree	20	10.8
	Higher secondary School (XI-XII)	65	35.1
	Middle Secondary School (IX-X)	20	10.8
	Lower secondary school (VII-VIII)	7	3.8
	Primary Education (PP-VI)	41	22.2
	No Education	13	7.0
Total	185	100.0	
3. Family Income	No income	16	8.6
	Less than Nu.5, 000	26	14.1
	Nu. 5,001 -10,000	34	18.4
	Nu 10,001 – 15,000	45	24.3
	Nu 15,001-20,000	35	18.9

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More than Nu. 20,000	29	15.7
Total	185	100.0

As presented in table 4.1, 31.95% of the respondents are male and 61.1 % of the respondents are female, out of which most of the respondents are higher secondary school graduates with 35.1% followed by primary education level with 22.2%. Least number of parents has master's degree represented by 3.2%. It also clearly showed that only 8.6% of the family has no income whereas majority of the family income falls in between Nu10,001 – 15,000 and 15.7 % of the family earns more than Nu.20,000.

4.2 The level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability

The collected findings are analyzed with the help of statistical tools i.e., mean and standard deviation as shown in tables given below.

Table 4.2 below represents the overall level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability.

Table 4. 2 The overall level of effectiveness

Variables	Mean Std.	Level of Deviation	Effectiveness
Diverse Background	4.04	.82	High
Flexibility and Accessibility	3.93	.78	High
Acceptability	4.10	.73	High
Average	4.02	.78	High

It is inferred that the parents' perception on the overall level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning was high with the average mean score of 4.02. As per the table above, the parents perceived that the level of effectiveness of all the variables was high with mean score of 4.04, 3.93 and 4.10 respectively.

The following table 4.3 to 4.5 will represent the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning based on the variables individually and in detail.

Table 4.3 The level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background

Diverse Background	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of Effectiveness
My child has access to device for online learning.	4.13	.70	High
I bought a personal phone for my child.	3.14	1.35	Moderate
I have access to internet connection.	4.24	.76	Highest
I give my child full support in his EIE learning	4.50	.61	Highest
I spend more than Nu.500 per month for online learning	4.30	.80	Highest
I can guide my child complete his assignments	4.41	.69	Highest
I read with my child when I am free	4.10	.83	High
I use other resources (YouTube, Google and Facebook, others) to enhance my child's learning.	4.10	.82	High
My child spends enough time playing outdoor games daily.	3.46	.89	High
I have maintained peaceful learning environment for my child.	4.01	.73	High
Average	4.04	0.82	High

The table 4.3 showed that the parents' perception on the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background at high level with the average score of

4.04. The statement, "I give my child full support in his EiE learning" was rated highest with mean score of 4.50, whereas the statement, "I bought a personal phone for my child" was rated moderate with mean score of 3.14. Though the parents encourages and supports their children for EiE online teaching and learning, many of them are also against buying personal phones for their child. The reason for such finding could be because of their financial constraint or some believed that gadgets dominate child's time

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and space. Most of the statements were perceived high but statements such as having internet connection, spending more than Nu.500 on online learning and guiding the children with their assignments were also rated highest. From this, it's very evident that diverse background does not affect EiE online teaching and learning from parents' perspective.

Table 4.4 The level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to flexibility and accessibility

Flexibility and Accessibility	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of Effectiveness
My child has access to EIE online teaching and learning anytime, anywhere.	3.96	.74	High
My child gets enough time to write and submit the assignments.	4.37	.59	Highest
I get enough time for my office and personal work.	3.68	.82	High
I spent enough time with my child on EIE online learning.	3.86	.80	High
The teacher provides enough and easy content at a time which helps the child to understand and do the assignments on time.	4.15	.74	High
The teacher provides immediate feedback on the assignments submitted.	4.10	.80	High
Video clips and learning materials are well organised and to the standard.	4.10	.65	High
The teacher explains the contents clearly which helps the child to easily understand.	4.08	.74	High
My child spends few hours helping with household chores.	3.68	.89	High
My child shows interest in online teaching and learning.	3.32	1.02	Moderate
Average	3.93	.78	High

The parents' perception on the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning with respect to flexibility and accessibility was shown high with mean score of 3.93. Most of the statements under this variable were rated high but the statement which states "My child gets enough time to write and submit the assignments", was rated highest with mean score of 4.37. However, the statement stating, "My child shows interest in online teaching and learning" was revealed moderate with the mean score of 3.32. It can be understood that though the parents were encouraging, guiding and supporting their child with EiE online learning, most of the children were showing least interest on it. From the finding above, it can be perceived that EiE online teaching and learning in terms of flexibility and accessibility was effective and meets the expectation of the parents.

Table 4.5 The level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to acceptability

Acceptability	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of Effectiveness
I see my child interacting with the teacher frequently	3.37	.95	Moderate
I co-operate with the teachers with any kind of activity	4.18	.67	High
I am comfortable using Wechat App	4.21	.78	Highest
My child's teacher is approachable when asked for support.	4.31	.68	Highest
I correct my child's work before submitting the work to the teacher.	4.32	.74	Highest
I feel comfortable to receive feedback from my child's teacher on the work submitted	4.36	.65	Highest
I let my child correct the work instantly after the feedback.	4.32	.62	Highest
EIE online teaching and learning helps my child to learn the lessons effectively.	4.01	.74	High
EIE lessons are simple and to the level of my child.	3.88	.78	High
My child can complete the lesson within the stipulated time.	4.03	.72	High
Average	4.10	.73	High

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As per table 4.5, the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning with respect to acceptability was rated high with the average score of 4.10, out of which item 3,4,5,6,and

7 were rated highest. From these five items, item 6, "I feel comfortable to receive feedback from my child's teacher on the work submitted" has the highest mean score of 4.36. The item 1, "I see my child interacting with the teacher frequently" has least mean score of 3.37 and was perceived moderate. It can be supposed that the parents were contented with the teachers act such as being approachable, correcting the assignments and providing feedback but it seems that children were reluctant to respond or interact with their teacher. But overall, it can be concluded that EiE online teaching and learning in respect to acceptability was effective as per parents' perception. In summary, it is concluded that the EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility, and acceptability was very effective as per the parents' perspective.

4.3 Content Analysis

The following open-ended questions were also given to seek some measures and guidelines to enhance the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning.

1. Do you find Education in Emergency online teaching and learning effective? How?

For this question, most of the parents feels that EiE online teaching and learning is effective as their child are kept engaged and can continue with their studies even during such situation. They expressed that they can spend quality time with their children and even gain extra knowledge while guiding their children. Moreover, the children are learning and updating with the use of advance digital technology. However, for those parents who are uneducated and have low family income, it's difficult for them to guide their children whereby children losses interest in studies. They couldn't afford the data and personal phone for their child which made it difficult for their children to do the activities and submit on time. Some of the parents also stated that children are mostly found playing games and browsing other apps such as Facebook, Tiktok, watching television and spending less time on studying.

2. Can you suggest some of the ways/means to improve EiE online teaching and learning?

Though most of the parents were satisfied with EiE online teaching and some of the parents who are uneducated prefer more of video lessons and video conferencing rather than just providing activities and instructions. The parents also suggested providing more examples and giving clear instructions and explanations verbally. They would like to see more discussion taking place between the teacher and children and among children themselves with respect to the lesson. They also suggested to find out those parents who are uneducated, how many children doesn't have access to smart phone and internet connection, and explore different methods to reach out to those children to avoid education disparity.

3. What is your overall view on EIE online teaching and learning and any recommendations?

Most of the parents feels that face to face classroom teaching is the most effective and progressive method of teaching and learning for their children but during pandemic, they find EiE online teaching and learning very good initiative to keep their children engaged, continue with their studies and at least learn something than just wasting a whole year. Offer of free data and talk time was highly recommended by most of the parents especially for those parents who cannot afford. Though there are lots of challenges faced by the teachers, parents and children, almost all of them were very thankful to the government and MOE for enchanting such initiative during the times of need.

DISCUSSION

The analysis of findings is presented in this chapter. This study is intended to find the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning as per the parents' perspective and the findings of this study would be discussed in accordance with the objectives of the research as follows:

5.1 Analysis of the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability

5.2 Analysis on measures and guidelines for the enhancement of the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning.

5.1 Analysis of the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability

The research findings revealed that the overall level of the effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to all the variables (diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability) falls in high level with average score of 4.02. From the three variables, the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning based on acceptability was rated highest and the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning based on flexibility and accessibility was rated lowest with average score of 4.10 and 3.93 respectively. As per the finding, the parents' perception on the level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background was shown high with the mean score of 4.02 which indicates that diverse background does not affect EiE online teaching and learning from parents' perspective. The reason to account for such findings could be our parents are mostly earning or they are not deprived of providing resources to their children. Moreover the schools in our country reach out

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to the students who need support and guidance. From data collected and analyzed, it was shown that only 7% of the parents are uneducated and 16 parents said they have no income source. This shows that most of the parents can provide learning resources to their children. The finding from this study also revealed that most of the students had an access to device for online learning. As stated by Hameed et.al (2016) students who are not exposed to computer faces problem but in our country our delivery of lessons are mostly through mobile app (Wechat and Google classroom) where everyone are competent in using it. The result on buying personal phone for their children showed moderate with mean score of 3.14 which indicate that parents are not in favor of buying personal phone. The reason could be not applicable and sudden change in learning during this pandemic had not prepared parents to buy personal phone for their kids. The level of effectiveness of EiE online teaching and learning in respect to flexibility was rated high with means score of 3.93. Such finding could be because of the time availability and accessibility of lesson. The teachers provide the lesson through the most convenient mode where most of the parents and students can easily access. In our Bhutanese context online learning by the primary children for the first time with access to well organized learning materials and relevant video clips provides better learning outcomes and high level of parents satisfaction as presented in the result with mean score of 4.10. Therefore, designing and implementing interactive and selecting good instructional activities which satisfy the students' learning needs were recommended to enhance effective online teaching and learning (Lim, nd). The level of effectiveness of EiE online learning in respect to acceptability was shown high with the mean score of 4.10 indicates that parents are contented with online learning for their children. They felt that online learning atleast promote their child's learning in this period of pandemic. The questions on teacher approachable, timely feedback, relevant lesson and using Wechat app validates high level of parent's acceptance of online teaching and learning. This concludes that EiE online teaching and learning is effective as per the parents based on the three variables selected and analysed. The result also indicated most of the positive aspect with some limitations. Positive points like parents being comfortable using the electronic devices, supporting their children, time flexible, and relevant lesson and contant feedback from the teachers. And limitation such as developing less interest and less interaction with the teachers needs to be enhanced.

5.2 Analysis on measures and guidelines for the enhancement of the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning

The perception of parents on EIE online teaching and learning was positive as it helped to keep their child engaged and continue their studies even during the pandemic. Spending quality time, guiding their children, exploring and learning was mostly expressed by the parents. It was found out that learning from textbook in the classroom enhances only lower order to mid-order cognitive processes such as remembering, understanding, applying and analyzing whereas learning online facilitate high order skills in Bloom's Taxonomy as per Lau et al (2017).

The parents also prefer more discussion and collaboration with teachers and among students themselves which will enhance the student's interest on online teaching and learning. In addition, designing and implementing interactive and selecting good instructional activities also enhances effective online teaching and learning (Lim, nd).

In order to avoid the disparity, the parents suggested finding out those children who are deprived of smart phone and internet connection and explore different means to reach out to them. However, the parents suggested providing free data and talking time to those who cannot afford to access online teaching and learning in this study as the quality of students learning will be improved

CONCLUSIONS

This chapter will conclude the findings of the study and provide the recommendations as follows: 6.1 Conclusions

6.1.1 General Information

6.1.2 The level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability

6.1.3 Analysis on measures and guidelines for the enhancement of the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning.

6.2 Limitation of the study

6.3 Recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

The objective of this study was to find out the parents' perception on level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability and to provide some measures to enhance the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning. The study used quantitative research method by administering 185 questionnaires with few open ended questions to 185 parents of students studying in classes PP to 6. All the questionnaires were completed, collected and analyzed.

6.1.1 General Information

The study consists of 185 respondents of which 31.95% of the respondents are male and 61.1 % are female. Most of the respondents are higher secondary school graduates (35.1%), few of them were uneducated (7%) and least number of parents has master's degree

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(3.2%). It was also concluded that most of the family income falls in between Nu10,001 – 15,000 and 15.7 % of the family earns more than Nu.20,000, and only 8.6% of the family has no income.

6.1.2 The level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability

The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was employed to study perception of parents on the level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning in respect to diverse background, flexibility and accessibility and acceptability. The overall level of effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning was high with the average mean score of 4.02 and the level of effectiveness of all the variables were also perceived high with mean score of 4.04 for diverse background, 3.93 for flexibility and 4.10 for acceptability as per parents perception.

6.1.3 Analysis on measures and guidelines for the enhancement of the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning

To enhance the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning, most of the parents suggested various measures as follows:

- i. Providing video lesson and conducting video teaching, so that those students who are deprived of parent's guidance could acquire knowledge equivalent to those with students who gets guidance from their parents.
- ii. Exploring various means to reach out to those students without smartphones and internet connectivity to avoid the education disparity among the students.
- iii. In order to have access to online teaching and learning equally by all the students, free data and talk time was proposed by the parents
- iv. More discussions, instructional activities, examples, clear explanation and verbal instruction were also anticipated by the parents to make EIE online teaching and learning more effective.

6.2 Limitation of the study

Finding the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning was affected by the responses given by the parents. This EIE was carried out for short duration of nine months and the participants were not able to identify its effectiveness totally. Therefore the responses received through the class teachers lack authenticity. It can be forged or false responses. The responses received from the parents also lack gender equality as we have more of female responders. If the responses received had equal numbers, then it means parents are equally participating in the learning of their child.

6.3 Recommendation

To see the effectiveness of EIE online teaching and learning, the study should be carried out for longer duration and the data collection should be collected by visiting the responder individually so that the responses are true and genuine. The sample should be more to come up with reliable interpretation.

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